

**THE ROLE OF YAJURVEDA AND AYURVEDA IN PREVENTION OF LIFESTYLE
DISORDERS DUE TO MENTAL HEALTH**

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ABSTRACT

Lifestyle diseases are non-communicable disorders that develop primarily as a result of unhealthy lifestyle practices and behavioural patterns. Lifestyle diseases, including Hypertension, type 2 diabetes, obesity and cardiovascular disorders are strongly influenced by mental health factors such as stress, anxiety and depression. Lifestyle diseases are responsible for over 70% of deaths worldwide, according to WHO. Many of these conditions are directly or indirectly linked to stress, anxiety, depression. Ayurveda is the oldest known knowledge of healthcare. The Ayurvedic system of healing is believed to be based on eminent compilations of Vedas. The Yajurvedic ethical- spiritual practices and Ayurvedic lifestyle interventions offers a psychological and physiological aspects of health to preventive and promotive lifestyle disorders arising from mental health imbalances. Yajurveda emphasizes discipline, ethical conduct and ritual practices which reduce mental stress, enhance self- control and emotional stability. Ayurveda integrates principles with includes Dincharya (Daily routines), Ritucharya (Seasonal regimen), Aachar rasayana and Sadvritta (code of conduct) to directly manage the body- mind balance. All references for the concept of Ayurveda regimen is studied from charak samhita and Ashtang Hriday.

KEYWORDS: *Yajurveda, Ayurveda, Lifestyle diseases, Mental Health, Dincharya, Ritucharya, Sadvritta.***INTRODUCTION**

Mental welfare is never recognized as the goal of human life. Mental health is a core component of overall health. Mental health and lifestyle are deeply interconnected. Mental health is a state of mental well being that enables people to cope with the stress, realize abilities, learn work well and contribute to community.^[1] Lifestyle disorders have become a major public health burden globally. Mental health disturbances such as chronic stress, anxiety, lack of emotional regulation leads to lifestyle disorders. The Yajurveda emphasize that health is sustained by Rta(cosmic order) and Dharma (Righteous conduct) when violate these imbalance arises in mind and body which leads to stress, loss of mental peace and diseases. Yajurveda speaks of balance in mind, speech and action as essential for well- being. When a person loses his intelligence, patience and memory and commits inauspicious acts that are harmful, then those inauspicious acts are called 'Pragyaparadha'.^[2]

Ayurveda is based on three fundamental principles: Hetu, Linga, Aushadha.^[3] Hetu that leads to diseases. By identifying Hetu helps us remove or avoid the root triggers before disease manifest. Nidan Parivarjana is the first step to stop mental stress from progressing into lifestyle disorders. Aushadha include not just medicines but also lifestyle and mental discipline, the approach is Satvavajaya Chikitsa, by strengthening Satvaguna and reducing Rajas and Tamas.

AIM

Fundamental principles of mental health described in Yajurveda and Ayurveda Samhitas for preventing lifestyle diseases.

OBJECTIVE

✓ To evaluate the principles of Yajurveda for healthy life.

✓ To understand and explain principles related to mental health to prevent lifestyle diseases.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Materials: Ayurvedic classical texts, Yajurveda, Journal, Internet.

Methods: Literary review.

- Nidan parivarjana
- Dincharya
- Ritucharya
- Dharniyavega
- Sadvritta (ideal routine)
- Aachar rasayan (way of good conduct)
- Satvavjaya chikitsa

PREVENTIVE PRINCIPLES IN YAJURVEDA

The Yajurveda is especially practical in prescribing discipline, rituals and inner control, which connect directly to prevention of psychosomatic and lifestyle diseases.

1. **Concept of mental balance in Yajurveda-** Yajurveda often invokes prayers for mental clarity, peace and self restraint. May my mind have auspicious, healthy resolutions.^[4] This highlights prevention at the thought level- lifestyle diseases arise when mental stress and unhealthy desires dominate.
2. **Siva Sankalpa Sukta (Healthy Intentions)-** Emphasizes cultivating positive thoughts and self-discipline prevents stress, addictions and aggression that the root cause of lifestyle diseases.
3. **Yajna (Sacrificial discipline)-** Reduce selfishness, stress and isolation that improves mental well-being. The main pillars of the Yajna like Agni and Vayu are helpful in human happiness and prosperity. They are the protectors of all, they make us happy.^[5]
4. **Mantra Therapy -** Repetition of sacred sounds (Om, Swasti chants) calms the nervous system to prevent stress, anxiety and insomnia these are risk factors for heart diseases and metabolic disorders.
5. **Rta (Cosmic order) and discipline-** Yajurveda ties health with alignment to rita (natural law) prevents major lifestyle diseases.

PREVENTIVE PRINCIPLES IN AYURVEDA

1. **Nidan Parivarjan-** Avoidance of causative factors (Dietary causes, behavioural causes, psychological causes) to stop mental stress from progressing into lifestyle diseases. Hetu sevana is

the root cause of diseases and their avoidance is the primary treatment.

2. **Dincharya (Daily Routine)-** Dincharya is one of the strongest preventive pillars it directly addresses the root of lifestyle diseases by regulating mind, body and senses in harmony. Its aim to maintain equilibrium of Dosh, Agni, Dhatu and Manas through regulated habits.

Daily routine in shortly

- Morning- waking up at brhmamuhurt (2 hrs before sun rise) enhances Sattva, reduces mental stress.
- Brushing teeth should be made of a fresh twig of nimb, khadir, karanj prevention of systemic diseases linked to oral health.
- Gargles with medicated oil to being healthy gums.
- Anjana and Nasya prevents eye/ ENT disorders, improves prana flow.
- Abhyanga (oil massage) nourishes dhatus, prevents stress, fatigue, Vata disorders.
- Vyayama (Exercise) -improve digestion, strength metabolism, prevent obesity and cardiac issues.
- Snana (Bathing) - improves alertness, hygiene, mental freshness.

3. **Ritucharya -** Ritu (season), charya (regimen/ discipline) to maintain dosa balance and prevent seasonal disorders and lifestyle diseases. Seasonal changes affect mood and psychology (fear in varsa, irritability in sarad, lethargy in sisira). Following Ritucharya maintains Sattva and prevents seasonal depression, anxiety, irritability.

Ritucharya in Shorts

Adan kal (Jan to june) consist of shisir, basant, grishm. Visarg kal (July to dec) consist of varsha, sharad, hemant. In Adan kal body strength decreasing and Visarg kal body strength increasing in manner. Every season brings a shift in dosa like in shisir kapha dominance, grishm Vata accumulation, sharad pitta aggravation.

4. **Dharniya Vega-** Acharyas classify urges into two types: Adharniyavega and Dharniya vega. A man who desires welfare in this world and the next should become self-controlled and restrain the speeds of greed, envy, hatred, passion and others.^[6] Dharniya vegas include krodha, lobha, Moha, Raga, Soka these vegas are linked to manas (mind) and Sattva (mental strength). If they uncontrolled, disturb Rajas and Tamas and eventually manifest as lifestyle diseases.

Table No. 1: Dharniya Vegas Lead to Lifestyle Diseases.

S.No.	Dharniya Vegas	Sharirik & Mansik Dosh	Lifestyle Diseases
1	Krodha (Anger)	Pitta ↑, Rajas	Hypertension, Cardio Vascular
2	Soka (Grief)	Vata ↑, Tamas ↑	Depression Insomnia
3	Lobha (Greed)	Kapha ↑, Rajas ↑	Obesity, Type 2 Diabetes
4	Moha (Attachment/Delusion)	Kapha ↑, Tamas ↑	Addictive behaviours (Alcohol, Smoking) Social Stress

5	Raga (Excessive Passion, Attachment)	Rajas ↑	Stress – Related condition
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5. Sadvritta- It is the first line of prevention in ayurveda. Sadvritta related to social, emotional, psychological and ethical aspects of life. Sadvritta provides the ideal code of conduct which preventing dosa- prakopa, correcting pragraapradh, enhancing sattva, promoting balance in body- mind.

6. Aachar Rasayan- Aachar Rasayan is the ayurvedic way of preventive and promotive health strategy against lifestyle diseases. A person who avoid anger, self - controlled and disciplined, control over senses, follow Dharma, maintain purity of body, mind and speech leads to Dirghayu (longevity), Smriti- Medhavrdhdi (enhanced memory), Arogya (disease prevention), Sattva vrdhdi (purity of mind, reduction of Rajas and Tamas).

Table No. 2: Aachar Rasayan Preventive Aspects.

Aachar Rasayan Principle	Lifestyle Disease Prevented
Anger Control, Forgiveness	Hypertension, CAD Stroke
Moderation, Self-Discipline	Obesity, Diabetes, Metabolic Syndrome
Non-Violence, compassion	Stress, Anxiety, Depression
Truthfulness, Calm Mind	Psychosomatics disorders (IBS, Psoriasis)
Avoidance of alcohol & excess	Addiction, Liver disease

7. Satvavajaya chikitsa- Preventing the mind from eating and drinking that is harmful to the health of body.^[7] Ayurvedic psychotherapy, aimed to prevents and manages lifestyle diseases by controlling mind, reducing mental stress, strengthens will power and promoting mental clarity (Sattva).

CONCLUSION

The union of Yajurveda teachings and Ayurvedic principles offers a comprehensive blueprint for safeguarding mental health, thereby preventing lifestyle diseases and promoting longevity. Vedic texts Yajurveda having good intervention to prevent lifestyle disorder through promotion of mental calmness through Santi Mantras and Hymns, guidance of ethical living, Yajna teaches discipline, mindfulness and control over senses. Disturbances in mind (Chittodvega) are a primary cause of lifestyle disorders. Through Sadvritta (ethical conduct), Satvavajaya Chikitsa (Psychotherapy) Ayurveda prevents the onset and progression of lifestyle disorders induced by mental stress, making it a holistic preventive system in health management.

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